

Oxidation of some aromatic secondary alcohols by Cr^{VI} supported on Amberlyst A-26 (Cl⁻) : A kinetic and mechanistic investigation

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Abstract : A kinetic study of the controlled oxidation of some aromatic secondary alcohols by Cr^{VI} supported on Amberlyst A-26 (Cl⁻) were found to proceed through ester formation. The ester thus formed decomposes in a slow step and produces chromium(IV). Chromium(IV) is formed as an intermediate which will further oxidize another molecule of aromatic secondary alcohol because our oxidant was supported on polymeric material and generates a free radical in a fast step. The free radical reacts with another oxidant site in the polymeric reagent in a fast step leading to the formation of chromium(V). In the final step the intermediate chromium(V) reacts with secondary alcohol to produce ketone. Various thermodynamic activation parameters were also calculated at different temperatures.

Keywords : Kinetic, oxidation, Cr^{VI} supported, mechanism, Amberlyst A-26 (Cl⁻).

Introduction

Oxidations of organic compounds are quite important from synthetic and technological viewpoints. Many of the industrially used organic compounds like alcohols, aldehydes, ketones, carboxylic acids etc. can be produced by the use of suitable oxidizing agents¹⁻³.

In this article, we report the kinetics of the oxidation of substituted 1-phenylethanol using polymer supported chromic acid on Amberlyst A-26 (Cl⁻), a strong anion exchange resin is supported with chromium(VI) oxide and used as an oxidant. Although a large number of reagents are known in the literature^{4,5} for such transformation, there still appears a need to improve the existing oxidation methods⁶.

In synthetic organic chemistry, oxidation under phase transfer catalysis⁷ finds wide application, but using polymer supported oxidizing agents⁸ for kinetic and mechanistic studies are limited. The polymer supported oxidizing agent can be used and reused without loss of capacity, and also very easy to work up. Safety is the major factor of interest for the present study. By use of polymer supported oxidizing agent the side reaction decreases and the oxidation process stops at the product ketone only.

The oxidation of substituted benzyl alcohols by polymer supported chromic acid on Amberlyst A-26 (Cl⁻) and on Ambersep 900 (OH⁻) has been already reported⁸. Considering all these advantages the title reaction, in which polymer supported chromic acid is used as an oxidant, was investigated and the results are given below.

Results and discussion

The order of reaction with respect to oxidant is zero as the plots of absorbance against time were linear in all runs and the observed rate constants are fairly constant between 50 to 80 × 10⁻⁶ kg of the oxidant at constant concentration of solvent (1,4-dioxane, 5 × 10⁻³ dm³) and alcohols. The effect of oxidant on the zero order rate constant is shown in Table 1.

The kinetic study is carried out at different concentration of alcohols at constant concentration of solvent (1,4-dioxane, 5 × 10⁻³ dm³) and oxidant (70 × 10⁻⁶ kg) at 45 °C. The plot of absorbance against time was linear in all runs passing through origin. This shows that the reaction is zero order to concentration of alcohols (Table 2).

The zero order rate constant increases with increase in dielectric constant of the medium including $r^* < r$ (where r^* and r refer to the radii of activated complex and reac-

Table 1. Effect of change in concentration of oxidant on the rate of reaction at 45 °C

Alcohols	$k \times 10^{-6} \text{ (s}^{-1}\text{)}$			
	$50 \times 10^{-6} \text{ kg}$	$60 \times 10^{-6} \text{ kg}$	$70 \times 10^{-6} \text{ kg}$	$80 \times 10^{-6} \text{ kg}$
1-Phenylethanol	1.77	1.83	1.86	1.87
4-Fluorophenylethanol	2.20	2.21	2.22	2.25
4-Chlorophenylethanol	2.38	2.40	2.41	2.44
4-Bromophenylethanol	2.75	2.83	2.88	2.91

Table 2. Effect of change in concentration of alcohols on the rate of reaction

Alcohols	Alcohol $\times 10^{-6} \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ conc.}$	$k \times 10^{-6} \text{ (s}^{-1}\text{)}$			
		5	7.5	10.0	12.5
1-Phenylethanol	Alcohol $\times 10^{-6} \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ conc.}$	5.91	8.21	10.5	12.8
	$k \times 10^{-6} \text{ (s}^{-1}\text{)}$	2.13	2.22	2.33	2.44
4-Fluorophenylethanol	Alcohol $\times 10^{-6} \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ conc.}$	5.32	8.72	12.1	15.5
	$k \times 10^{-6} \text{ (s}^{-1}\text{)}$	2.40	2.41	2.45	2.50
4-Chlorophenylethanol	Alcohol $\times 10^{-6} \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ conc.}$	4.6	9.0	13.4	17.8
	$k \times 10^{-6} \text{ (s}^{-1}\text{)}$	2.80	2.88	2.91	3.11

tant species respectively) at constant alcohol concentration and constant concentrations of oxidant and solvent (1,4-dioxane, $5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ dm}^3$) at 45 °C as shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Effect of dielectric constant on the rate of reaction

Solvents	Dielectric constants	$k \times 10^{-6} \text{ (s}^{-1}\text{)}$			
		1-Phenyl-ethanol	4-Fluoro-phenyl-ethanol	4-Chloro-phenyl-ethanol	4-Bromo-phenyl-ethanol
Cyclohexane	1.983	1.25	1.54	1.66	2.33
CCl_4	2.175	1.50	1.71	2.00	2.16
1,4-Dioxane	2.288	1.86	2.22	2.41	2.88
Chloroform	4.806	2.16	2.62	2.83	3.55

The reaction was carried out between 40–55 °C at fixed concentrations of oxidant ($70 \times 10^{-6} \text{ kg L}$), solvent (1,4-dioxane, $5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ dm}^3$) and alcohol (Table 4). The values of thermodynamic parameters like enthalpy of activation (ΔH^\ddagger), entropy of activation (ΔS^\ddagger), free energy of activation (ΔG^\ddagger) and energy of activation (E_a) were

Table 4. Effect of temperature on the rate of reaction

Alcohols	$k \times 10^{-6} \text{ (s}^{-1}\text{)}$			
	40 °C	45 °C	50 °C	55 °C
1-Phenylethanol	1.66	1.86	2.22	2.66
4-Fluorophenylethanol	2.00	2.22	2.75	3.33
4-Chlorophenylethanol	2.13	2.41	2.92	3.62
4-Bromophenylethanol	2.25	2.88	3.32	3.92

calculated from the measurements of the rates at 40, 45, 50 and 55 °C. The thermodynamic parameters were evaluated from $\log k$ versus $1/T$ plots (Table 5).

Table 5. Thermodynamic parameters

Alcohols	Thermodynamic parameters			
	ΔH^\ddagger (kJ)	ΔS^\ddagger ($\text{JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$)	ΔG^\ddagger (kJ mol^{-1})	E_a (kJ)
1-Phenylethanol	27.33 (± 0.60)	-54.60 (± 1.14)	101.25 (± 1.50)	52.00 (± 0.30)
4-Fluorophenylethanol	26.80 (± 0.70)	-54.82 (± 1.25)	100.70 (± 2.50)	47.86 (± 0.40)
4-Chlorophenylethanol	23.93 (± 0.85)	-57.14 (± 1.34)	100.49 (± 3.40)	46.40 (± 0.52)
4-Bromophenylethanol	21.04 (± 0.95)	-58.66 (± 1.55)	100.41 (± 3.90)	45.68 (± 0.69)

The reaction rates were determined at different molar concentration of alcohols and keeping the concentration of solvent (1,4-dioxane) and oxidant fixed, and were found to be zero order. Similarly, the rates were determined at different concentrations of oxidant keeping the concentrations of solvent (1,4-dioxane) and alcohol fixed. The order of the reaction was found to be zero.

The moderate values of ΔS^\ddagger , ΔH^\ddagger were favorable for electron transfer process. The moderate value of ΔH^\ddagger was due to a release of energy of solution changes in the transition state. The negative values of ΔS^\ddagger within the

range of radical reactions has been attributed⁹ to the nature of electron pairing and electron unpairing processes, and to the loss of degrees of freedom, formerly available to the reactions on the formation of a rigid transition state.

The values for the free energy of activation ΔG^\ddagger for all reactions were almost same. These suggest that probably the same mechanism prevails in all the reactions.

The energy of activation E_a determined from the slope of Arrhenius plots of $\log k$ versus $1/T$ and other parameters calculated are given in Table 5. Thus, the trend in E_a values and order of reactivity reveal that, the activation energy value is the highest for the slowest reaction and vice versa.

The energy of activation E_a reflects that the energy of activation for the different *para* substituted 1-phenylethanol is in the following order : 1-phenylethanol > 4-fluorophenylethanol > 4-chlorophenylethanol > 4-bromophenylethanol. On the contrary, rates of oxidation of these alcohols are found to be in the order : 1-phenylethanol < 4-fluorophenylethanol < 4-chlorophenylethanol < 4-bromophenylethanol.

The above results show that the rate of oxidation goes on increasing from 1-phenylethanol to 4-bromophenylethanol. Hence it is evident that the reaction is facilitated by electron withdrawing group at *para* position.

There were several paths proposed for subsequent reaction of chromium(IV), thus making possible a different mechanism for the oxidation of alcohols. The Westheimer and Watanabe^{10,11} shows subsequent steps must involve chromium(IV) as shown below (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

The conversion of Cr^{IV} to Cr^{III} has been established as proceeding via a disproportionation reaction^{12,13}. Westheimer then proposed that the oxidation of primary and secondary alcohols proceeded via the acid chromate esters as intermediates (Scheme 2).

Scheme 2

Our oxidant was supported on polymeric material, and then the intermediate chromium(IV) will further oxidize

another molecule of alcohol to produce a free radical. Thus based on the experimental results obtained for the oxidation of substituted 1-phenylethanol was found to be of zero order and the mechanism is given in Scheme 3. The mechanism involves an ester formation as preliminary steps¹⁴⁻¹⁷.

The ester formed will decompose into ketone and the intermediate chromium(IV) will be formed in the second and slow step.

The intermediate chromium(IV) thus formed will further react with another alcohol molecule to produce a free radical. The free radical formation in the reaction was confirmed by the polymerization of added acrylonitrile as well as acidified methanol into the reaction mixture.

Subsequently the free radical will react with another oxidant site in the polymeric reagent in a fast step leading to the formation of chromium(V).

The intermediate chromium(V) in the last step reacts with alcohol to produce ketone. The test for formation of chromium(V) and chromium(IV) by their characteristic induced oxidation of iodide and manganese(II)¹⁸ were not successful probably due to heterogeneity of the reaction mixture.

Scheme 3

Experimental

Preparation of polymer supported chromic acid :

The polymeric reagent [oxidant] was prepared according to the reported procedure¹⁹⁻²¹ starting from the chloride form of Amberlyst A-26 (Cl⁻), quaternary ammonium group (10×10^{-3} kg) was stirred with a saturated solution of chromium trioxide (5×10^{-3} kg) in water (30×10^{-3} dm³) for 30 min at room temperature using a magnetic stirrer. Chloride ion was readily displaced and HCrO₄⁻ form of resin was obtained in 30 min. The resulting resin was successively rinsed with water, acetone and ether and finally dried in vacuum at 50 °C for 5 h. The dried form of the resin was stored and used throughout the kinetic study.

The capacity of the chromate form of polymeric reagent was determined iodometrically. The capacity of the chromate form of Amberlyst A-26 (Cl⁻) resin 3.6 mmol/g, was used for the kinetic study throughout the work. Other chemicals like 1,4-dioxane (A.R.), chloroform, cyclohexane, carbon tetrachloride (Spectroscopic grade) and alcohols used were purified and stored.

Method of kinetics of oxidation procedure :

The kinetic measurement was initiated by a mixture of alcohol, oxidant (known amount) and solvent (5×10^3 dm³ of 1,4-dioxane) was stirred using a magnetic stirrer at constant temp. 45 ± 1 °C. The completion time of reaction was monitored with the help of thin layer chromatography. The course of reaction was monitored by withdrawing a known amount of aliquot with the help of a micropipette (care was taken, so that no solid particles were removed along with the solution). The aliquot thus withdrawn in a stoppered test tube containing 5×10^{-3} dm³ of 1,4-dioxane at a definite interval of time and optical density of all reaction mixture was measured at different wavelengths, corresponding to the wavelength of the ketone using Elico-SL 159 UV-Vis spectrophotometer.

Polymerization study :

The reaction was initiated by mixing oxidant, alcohol and solvent at 45 °C with continuous stirring. After 30 min, the reaction mixture was withdrawn in a test tube and acrylonitrile was added. The mixture after dilution with distilled water formed copious precipitate. Also the addition of acidified methanol into the reaction mixture formed white precipitate. The precipitation due to polymerization of acrylonitrile indicates the formation of a free radical in the reaction²². The presence of the free radical intermediate was confirmed by ESR spectrum.

Product analysis :

The product formed (ketone) was analyzed by UV spectrum, FTIR and also analyzed by its 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone derivative. The melting points of 2,4-DNP derivatives of ketones were recorded by open capillary method and uncorrected. Percentage yield of each product (ketone) isolated also calculated.

2,4-DNP derivatives of ketones	M.p. (°C)	λ_{max} (nm)	Yield (%)
(i) Acetophenone	237	245	89
(ii) 4-Fluoroacetophenone	234	265	84
(iii) 4-Chloroacetophenone	232	260	87
(iv) 4-Bromoacetophenone	230	257	90

The IR spectra were recorded on FT-IR 8400 Shimadzu model in KBr pellets.

Spectral data of ketones as follows :

Acetophenone : 1608.75 (-C=O), 3062.62 (-C-H), 1598.57 cm⁻¹ (aromatic >C=C<). 2,4-Fluoroacetophenone : 1649.14 (-C=O), 3005.10 (-C-H), 1431.18 cm⁻¹ (aromatic >C=C<). 3,4-Chloroacetophenone : 1647.21 (-C=O), 2960.73 (-C-H), 1571.99 cm⁻¹ (aromatic >C=C<). 4,4-Bromoacetophenone : 1678.22 (-C=O), 2924.88 (-C-H), 1587.82 cm⁻¹ (aromatic >C=C<).

Conclusion :

The linearity of absorbance against time plots and constancy of the zero order rate constants indicate that the reaction neither depends on the polymeric reagent nor on the alcohol concentration. This anomalous nature of the reaction may be because of the fact that the oxidant is taken in the form of a solid supported on polymer. Therefore, the prior equilibrium, before the rate determining step or the step in which actual reaction takes place giving the product does not seem to contribute to the total rate since they are occurring in different phase i.e. solid phase. This was observed in earlier study of benzoin oxidation by polymer supported *N*-bromosulphonamide²³.

According to Scheme 3, a second order rate law is expected. But since the first step of ester formation occurs in solid phase and assuming that this equilibrium does not contribute to the rate of reaction. We obtained zero order dependence with rate constant *k* of the second slow step in which product ketone is formed.

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